

Integrating digital media in foreign language teaching: Teachers' perceptions of digital competence

Migena Alimehmeti¹ and Kleada Agasi^{1,*}

¹University of Tirana, Faculty of Foreign Languages, Albania

*Correspondence: University of Tirana, Faculty of Foreign Languages, Tirana, Albania. E-mail: migena.alimehmeti@unitir.edu.al

Abstract

The purpose of this study is to identify aspects related to teachers' digital competencies in the pre-university system. A questionnaire was administered to 100 teachers across primary and secondary schools, focusing on: current practices in using digital platforms and tools, teachers' level of training and digital competence, and their perceptions of the impact of digital media on the teaching process. Findings indicate that while many teachers are aware of and employ digital resources, their use remains limited and uneven. Teachers demonstrate knowledge of essential digital skills, such as the critical evaluation of resources, ethical use of information technologies, and openness to continuous professional development. However, gaps remain in consistent application, access to infrastructure, and confidence in integrating new tools into everyday teaching. These findings highlight the need for targeted and continuous professional development programs, improved digital infrastructure, and institutional support to strengthen teachers' digital competence and ensure the effective integration of digital media in foreign language education.

Keywords: *Digital Competence; Teaching; Continuing Education; Digital Infrastructure.*

JEL Classification: I2; I23; Z13.

1. Introduction

Digital media are increasingly entering the classroom, opening new didactic opportunities, and thus changing the way of teaching. Digital teaching methods and tools play a key role in this regard. The means of communication technology have always marked the new structures of society, and schools are gradually losing their monopoly as the primary source of information. They facilitate collaboration and reinforce the role of information and non-textual communication using sound, images, and video. Students today find information and guidance on almost any topic they are interested in online.

Integrating digitized media in education requires a fundamental change of competencies in teachers to effectively use digital tools and resources in teaching and learning environments.

Based on the fact that digitization offers a wide range of tools and opportunities to enrich language learning and meet the diverse needs of students in an increasingly connected and technologically advanced world, the purpose of this study serves to draw out some of the aspects related to the competences of the teachers in the pre-university system and the possibilities in the efficient use of these tools in the lesson.

Ritter and Pedersen (Ritter & Pedersen, 2020) defines digital impact as the fact that, increasingly, analog data is converted to digital data or data is generated directly in digital form. Krumsvik speaks of an evolution of influential media (Krumsvik et al., 2013). According to him, the means of communication technology have always marked the new structures of society: we face the assumption that the invention of the computer had consequences for society as spectacular as the invention of language, writing, and printing.

The purpose of this study is to explore the extent to which foreign language teachers in Albania's pre-university system are equipped to integrate digital media into their pedagogical practice. Specifically, it examines current practices, teachers' training and competence levels, and their perceptions of the role of digital tools in language instruction.

A questionnaire was administered to 100 teachers across primary and secondary schools, focusing on: (a) current practices in using digital platforms and tools, (b) teachers' level of training and digital competence, and (c) their perceptions of the impact of digital media on the teaching process. The findings aim to contribute to the development of targeted professional development programs, resources, and support systems that empower teachers to harness the full

potential of digital technology in foreign language education, benefiting both educators and their students in a diverse and rapidly evolving educational landscape.

2. Literature Review

The didactic tools used for quality teaching should promote the development of students' skills, support independent learning, contain different and stimulating learning tasks, provide adequate treatment of the content, be written in clear language, be designed to encourage the learning process, and integrate the new media (Abdulrahman et al., 2020).

These characteristics show how these resources optimally encourage student learning and support teachers in their work (Aina & Abdulwasiiu, 2023). One of the characteristics of the increase in the use of digital tools in teaching is related to the loss of the monopoly on school information. With the increasing availability of online content, schools are gradually losing their monopoly as the primary source of information. Students today find information and guidance on almost any topic they are interested in online.

The evolution of media has led to the emergence of many new teaching and working tools that facilitate collaboration and reinforce the role of information and non-textual communication using sound, images, and video.

3. Methods and results

This study employs a mixed-methods approach to comprehensively investigate the integration of digital tools in foreign language education. By combining quantitative and qualitative research methods, the study aims to gather a broad range of insights from teachers, leading to a deeper understanding of their experiences, challenges, and training needs.

This study was conducted through a structured questionnaire administered to 100 foreign language teachers working in pre-university schools. The instrument aimed to collect quantitative data on teachers' use of digital media in the classroom, their level of digital competence, their training experiences, and their attitudes toward cultural diversity, copyright laws, and ethical practices in the use of digital resources. The questionnaire consisted of closed-ended questions, including multiple-choice and Likert-scale items, allowing for systematic analysis and comparison of responses. In addition to pedagogical and technical aspects, particular attention was given to ethical dimensions, such as respect for intellectual property, responsible digital citizenship, and the critical evaluation of online content.

A stratified random sampling method was employed to ensure representation across different grade levels and foreign languages taught. Participants were selected from various educational institutions in several Albanian cities, including Tirana, Durrës, Elbasan, Fier, Lushnje, Koplik, and Vorë. The collected data were analysed using statistical software (Excel) to generate descriptive insights into teachers' competencies, training needs, and ethical awareness in integrating digital tools into foreign language teaching.

They are foreign language teachers: English 66.7%, French 25%, other languages 8.3%. They teach in grades: first grade to fifth grade 8.3%, from 6th to ninth grade 25%, and from 10th to 12th grade, 66.7%. Regarding their seniority at work, 58.3% have from 0 to 5 years of work in teaching, 16.7 have 21-30 years, and the same 11-15 years of work, and 8.3% have about 16-20 years. We find that the largest percentage of participating teachers are young teachers with more up-to-date knowledge and training regarding using information technology tools in foreign language teaching. Potential limitations include self-selection bias, as those more comfortable with technology may be more inclined to participate. Additionally, the findings may not be generalizable to all foreign language teachers, as the sample may not represent all demographics.

4. Results and findings

In the section related to the current situation of the use of tools and digital platforms in foreign language classes, we find that 58.3% state that they rarely use the media and various information technology tools in the lesson, 25% constantly, and 16.7% often.

Statistics indicate that a significant majority, 58.3%, rarely incorporate media and information technology into their teaching. Meanwhile, only a quarter of educators consistently use these tools, and 16.7% do so often. This suggests a potential gap in integrating technology into language instruction. It might be worthwhile exploring the reasons behind the limited use, whether it is a lack of resources, training, or confidence in using digital tools effectively. Promoting professional development and sharing best practices could help increase the integration of these resources in the classroom. As the most used tools, they mention Smart Lab, the online teaching platform, computer, TBI interactive table, Telephone, PowerPoint, various Apps, and video projectors. The reasons why they use them are to make the lessons

more efficient and easier to teach, to get information, and to stimulate students' curiosity. So, to facilitate the learning process.

Among the difficulties that they encounter are mainly related to insufficient competence, the disconnection of the internet, having their own tools, the school providing no equipment, a lack of different digital tools, not all students have access to technology, and common projectors for several teachers. Regarding the time they need to prepare teaching materials to use through media and digitized tools, 58.3% state that they spend considerable time, 25% state that they spent time at the beginning and now use the same digital materials, and 16.7% emphasize that they spend a lot of time preparing and using digital tools. Regarding the continuation of their training and education, 83.3% of them request this. Most of them spend time preparing materials for digital use in teaching, and so many teachers say that they rarely use these media. 25% of them spent time in the beginning, when they made the first preparations, and now they feel more autonomous in their use, and we see that this percentage constantly uses information technology tools.

To the question of whether they have participated in training related to the recognition and use of media, platforms, and various information technology tools for teaching and learning purposes, 33.3% answered rarely, 41.7% constantly. 8.3% only once and 16.7% never. These statistics reveal a mixed landscape regarding teachers' training and competencies in using digital platforms and tools effectively. 41.7% say that such training is needed repeatedly, 33.3% claim that they are sufficient, and 25% say that they were insufficient. These responses provide further insight into teachers' perspectives on their training needs related to technology integration in education. 66.7% of them say that the training has increased significantly after distance learning during the pandemic, and 33.3 say that these trainings have not been that significant.

The responses regarding the impact of training after distance learning during the pandemic reveal valuable insights into the evolving landscape of teacher development and technology integration. 50% of the teachers affirm that training influences and helps in creating and strengthening the appropriate competencies for the use of digitized tools for teaching. But 50% of them say that these training courses have little effect on their ability in this field. To address the concerns raised by the 50% of teachers who feel that training has little effect, it is crucial to enhance the relevance and quality of training, provide ongoing support, showcase effective practices, gather feedback, and foster a culture of innovation. By doing so, we can help ensure that all teachers feel confident and competent in using digital tools, ultimately benefiting their teaching and student learning outcomes.

Regarding cooperation with others to improve their skills in the use of information technology tools and the digitization of their educational content, 66.7% state that they cooperate with their colleagues constantly, 16.7% sometimes, and 16.7% state that neither do their colleagues have the right skills. Working in a team brings visible efficiency. The teachers were asked if they sought the help of an IT expert. 41.7% state that they have requested it several times, 33.3% continuously. 16.7% never, and 8.3% state that they do not know any such. Also, 33.3% of teachers declare that they have constantly asked for help from students, 25% once, and 41.7% never. The availability of an IT expert has now become a necessity. The feedback regarding teachers seeking help from students highlights an interesting dynamic in the use of technology in education.

Related to the critical opinion about reliability, accuracy, and importance of using digitized information technology tools and content, 58.3% say that they are always attentive to these factors, 16.7% say that they use those media and tools for which they also have training, 16.7% ask colleagues, and the rest occasionally. The responses about teachers' critical opinions on the reliability, accuracy, and importance of using digitized information technology tools reveal a generally conscientious approach to technology integration in education.

Concerning the choice of appropriate digital resources, 50% of them are based on defining the objectives of students' understanding, 25% on the exact definition of experiences, and attractive learning strategies, 16.7% are not based on either objectives or strategies used, and 8.3% are based on ready-made digital plans that the media platform itself uses.

Regarding their readiness and suitability to explore new tools themselves, 83.3% do it constantly, and 16.7% rarely. The responses about teachers' readiness and suitability to explore new tools indicate a strong inclination toward professional growth and adaptability. The interpretation and use of the data created by the digital platform to transmit the educational content, 66.7% of the teachers do not encounter any difficulties. 25% encounter many difficulties, and 8.3% seek the assistance of an expert. The findings regarding teachers' experiences with interpreting and using data from digital platforms to transmit educational content provide valuable insights into their comfort levels and challenges.

Considering cultural diversity and inclusiveness in the integration of digitized media in the lesson, 58.3% always do it, 25% rarely, and 16.7% do not understand the question. The responses regarding teachers' attitudes toward

copyright law and digital citizenship indicate a mixed understanding of these important aspects of using digital resources in education. 41.7% of teachers respect copyright law, 41.7% promote digital citizenship among students, and 16.7% both. The most used platforms among them are Teams, Zoom, Google Meeting, YouTube, Office PowerPoint, Classroom, Blogger, Kahoot, Poppled, LAB, Slide, Duolingo Quiz, Interactive Book, Teams, Zoom, Google Meeting, and Live Binders. Teachers must constantly be updated with other new and latest platforms, which is not necessarily during their training and training sessions.

The teachers' opinions of the teachers regarding the influence of the media and digital platforms in the teaching process, the teachers state that: It positively affects the approach of the teacher-student relationship, as the latter are more involved during the lesson, as technology nowadays occupies a very large space in our lives. We must focus more on the use of ICT in education. We think it is a very good way to successfully teach. Secondary schools lack infrastructure, which affects the teacher's motivation in organizing an efficient lesson, since students are more interested in technology. It affects the teacher's motivation in organizing an efficient lesson, considering the fact that students are more interested in technology. Based on the answers given, we have that technology is very efficient during the educational process.

5. Discussion

The data collected regarding teachers' use of digital tools in foreign language lessons reveals important trends and areas for improvement in pedagogical practices. Here's a comprehensive discussion based on the key findings:

Use of digital tools in the classroom: With 58.3% of teachers rarely using media and technology in their lessons, it is clear that while there is an interest in integrating digital resources, many educators may lack the confidence or resources to do so consistently. 25% of those who use tools constantly suggest that there are effective practices in place that could be shared as models for their peers. The findings indicate a significant investment of time in preparing digital materials (58.3% spending considerable time). This suggests that while teachers are willing to engage with technology, the preparation process may be cumbersome, leading to underutilization in the classroom.

Competencies and training needs: With 83.3% of teachers expressing a desire for further training, there is a clear demand for ongoing professional development in using digital tools. The mixed responses about their training experiences highlight the need for more accessible and relevant training sessions that address specific needs. A large percentage (66.7%) of teachers do not face difficulties interpreting and using data from digital platforms. However, the 25% who encounter many challenges indicate a potential gap in understanding or access to necessary resources.

Cultural diversity and inclusiveness: The high percentage (58.3%) of teachers who always consider cultural diversity when selecting digital resources is encouraging. However, the 25% who rarely do so highlight a critical need for clearer guidelines and training on how to effectively incorporate diverse perspectives in educational content. The fact that 16.7% of teachers did not understand the question about cultural diversity suggests that there may be a need for more comprehensive discussions about what inclusivity means in the context of digital education.

Respect for copyright and digital citizenship: The equal split (41.7% each) between teachers who respect copyright law and those who promote digital citizenship indicates a need for a more integrated approach that combines both elements. The small percentage (16.7%) doing both suggests opportunities for training that encompasses both areas to create a holistic understanding of ethical digital practices.

Collaboration and support systems: The findings highlight significant collaboration among teachers (66.7% cooperate with colleagues), suggesting that fostering a collaborative culture can enhance the collective knowledge and use of digital tools. Encouraging shared experiences can help overcome individual challenges and enhance overall efficacy. The willingness of 41.7% of teachers to seek IT expert help demonstrates an acknowledgment of the challenges they face. This suggests that providing regular access to IT support could further enhance teachers' comfort with technology.

Recommendations for Future Action

Strengthening the integration of digital media in foreign language education requires a comprehensive and strategic approach centred on enhanced professional development. Targeted training programs should be designed to support teachers in the effective pedagogical use of digital tools, the interpretation of data generated by learning platforms, and the meaningful integration of cultural diversity into classroom practices.

Equally important is the creation of collaborative and supportive professional environments. Schools should foster peer mentoring initiatives and shared planning sessions where teachers can exchange experiences, strategies, and

digital resources. Establishing ongoing support structures, such as access to IT experts and regular professional check-ins, can help educators address challenges and consolidate successful practices.

Digital technologies offer wide-ranging opportunities to enrich teaching and learning processes. Teachers can access numerous online resources, including videos, audio materials, interactive games, language learning applications, educational websites, and professional discussion forums. (Zakirova et al., 2021). They can also design their own digital materials, such as presentations, interactive exercises, quizzes, blogs, podcasts, and instructional videos, tailored to the specific needs and learning profiles of their students.

Moreover, digital platforms provide efficient mechanisms for assessing student progress, monitoring performance, and delivering personalized feedback (Brugliera, 2024). They generate valuable data that can inform instructional decision-making and enhance learning outcomes. Teachers can also engage in continuous professional growth by participating in webinars, accessing online training materials, and sharing best practices within professional networks (Li et al., 2022). Ultimately, the effective integration of digitized media in education necessitates a transformation in teachers' competencies, ensuring they are equipped to navigate digital environments confidently, ethically, and pedagogically.

A further implication of this study concerns educational policy and institutional leadership. Beyond individual teacher training, systemic efforts are required to align curriculum frameworks, assessment practices, and infrastructure investments with the demands of digital transformation. Policymakers and school leaders should ensure equitable access to technological resources, embed digital competence standards within teacher evaluation and professional growth models, and promote a coherent vision that integrates pedagogy, ethics, and inclusivity. Such coordinated action can create sustainable conditions for meaningful and long-term digital innovation in education.

6. Conclusions

The findings indicate that teachers demonstrate a strong willingness to adapt to the evolving demands of digital education. The majority express openness to exploring new digital tools and integrating them into their teaching practices, reflecting a positive attitude toward innovation and change. This enthusiasm represents a valuable foundation for future professional development initiatives aimed at strengthening teachers' skills, confidence, and pedagogical effectiveness. At the same time, the clear demand for ongoing and targeted training highlights the necessity of structured professional development programs that emphasize the practical application of digital tools, the interpretation of educational data, and the meaningful integration of cultural diversity into lesson planning. Collaboration among teachers also emerges as a significant asset, as peer support, mentoring, and shared experiences can facilitate the exchange of best practices and help address common challenges related to technology integration.

In addition, the study underscores the importance of reinforcing ethical awareness and cultural responsiveness in digital education. While many teachers demonstrate familiarity with copyright regulations and the principles of digital citizenship, a more integrated, coherent framework is needed to ensure responsible, ethical digital use. Similarly, although most participants consider cultural diversity in lesson planning, further clarification, guidance, and resources are required to promote genuine inclusivity in educational content. By addressing these dimensions through targeted interventions and by fostering a supportive institutional environment, schools can enhance teachers' capacity to use digital tools effectively, ethically, and inclusively, ultimately contributing to more engaging, equitable, and high-quality learning experiences for all students.

References

- Abdulrahman, M. D., Faruk, N., Oloyede, A. A., Surajudeen-Bakinde, N. T., Olawoyin, L. A., Mejabi, O. V., Imam-Fulani, Y. O., Fahm, A. O., & Azeez, A. L. (2020). Multimedia tools in the teaching and learning processes: A systematic review. *Heliyon*, 6(11), e05312. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.heliyon.2020.e05312>
- Aina, J. K., & Abdulwasiu, A. A. (2023). Teachers' Effective Use of Educational Resources and Their Effect on Students' Learning. *ÜNİVERSİTEPARK Bülten*, 12(2). <https://doi.org/10.22521/unibulletin.2023.122.4>
- Brugliera, P. (2024). The Effectiveness of Digital Learning Platforms in Enhancing Student Engagement and Academic Performance. *Journal of Education, Humanities, and Social Research*, 1(1), 26–36. <https://doi.org/10.70088/xq3gy756>
- Dancaş, D., Štempeľová, I., Takáč, O., & Annuš, N. (2023). Digital tools in education. *International Journal of Advanced Natural Sciences and Engineering Researches*, 7(4), 289–294. <https://doi.org/10.59287/ijanser.717>

- Kozma, R. B., & Isaacs, S. (Eds.). (2011). *Transforming education: The power of ICT policies*. United Nations Educational, Scientific and Cultural Organization.
- Krumsvik, A. H., Storsul, T., Kung, L., Dogruel, L., Steensen, S., Liestøl, G., Baumann, S., Skogerbø, E., Doyle, G., Lindmark, S., Heritiana Ranaivoson, Donders, K., Ballon, P., Lomborg, S., Helles, R., Bakker, P., Davis, C. H., Jennes, I., Pierson, J., ...Müller, K. (2013). *Media Innovations: A Multidisciplinary Study of Change (2013)*. Nordicom. <https://doi.org/10.13140/2.1.1328.9284>
- Lai, B., Tan, K. H., He, M., Mohd Said, N.-E., & Muslim, N. (2022). The Roles of Non-Textual Elements in Sustaining ESL and EFL Learning: A Scoping Review. *Sustainability*, 14(16), 10292. <https://doi.org/10.3390/su141610292>
- Li, X., Bergin, C., & Olsen, A. A. (2022). Positive teacher-student relationships may lead to better teaching. *Learning and Instruction*, 80, 101581. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.learninstruc.2022.101581>
- McDiarmid, G. W., & Zhao (赵勇), Y. (2023). Time to Rethink: Educating for a Technology-Transformed World. *ECNU Review of Education*, 6(2), 189–214. <https://doi.org/10.1177/20965311221076493>
- Ritter, T., & Pedersen, C. L. (2020). Digitization capability and the digitalization of business models in business-to-business firms: Past, present, and future. *Industrial Marketing Management*, 86, 180–190. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.indmarman.2019.11.019>
- Tadjiyeva, M. D. (2023). The Use of Educational Apps as Didactic Tools in Teaching English as a Second Language. *European Journal of Higher Education and Academic Advancement*, 1(1), 224–228. <https://doi.org/10.61796/ejheaa.v1i1.184>
- Zakirova, E., Kulikova, E., & Medvedeva, E. (2021). Digital educational resources for English language studies: Teachers and learners' attitude. *SHS Web of Conferences*, 106, 03016. <https://doi.org/10.1051/shsconf/202110603016>
- UNESCO. [Wyatt-Smith, Claire](#), [Lingard, Bob](#), [Heck, Elizabeth](#). Evaluations numériques des apprentissages et les mégadonnées : conséquences sur le professionnalisme des enseignants. ED-2019/WP/3

Acknowledgments: We express our gratitude to all teachers of the pre-university system who participated in this study by giving their contribution in answering the questions of the questionnaire. “During the preparation of this manuscript/study, the authors used Grammarly Assistant for linguistic editing and correct sentence construction. The authors have reviewed and edited the output and take full responsibility for the content of this publication.”

Funding: This research received no external funding.

Declaration: We declare that we have used Grammarly Assistant for language editing purposes. We, the authors, confirm and are responsible for the originality, accuracy, validity, and integrity of all content presented. Also, the data and findings presented are accurate and have not been fabricated, falsified, or manipulated. We agree to provide supporting data if requested.

Biographical Note: Migena Alimehmeti is Lecturer in the Department of French Language, Faculty of Foreign Languages, University of Tirana. Albania. Field of study: General linguistics, didactics, teaching methodology, critical thinking, applied French grammar, French morphology, text typology, methodology of university work, French language of specialty, master's and doctoral research supervisor. Further studies: Master of Science in Public Administration, Faculty of Economics, UT, Faculty of Law, UT. Author of several scientific articles and international conferences. Trainer for pre-university education teachers on teaching-learning methods and critical-creative thinking. Email: migena.alimehmeti@unitir.edu.al. Kleada Agasi is Lecturer in the Department of Foreign Languages, Faculty of Foreign Languages, Tirana, University of Tirana. Albania. Academic part-time staff for 3 years. Field of study: English Teaching, Business English, Finance English, and Marketing English. Participation in various national and international conferences. Author of several scientific articles in the field of education. Various trainings related to teaching methods and digital competences are organized in Albania and abroad. Participation in scientific activities organized by the Department, Faculty, University, and other Institutions. kleada_agasi@yahoo.com.

Submitted: October 2024 ▪ Revision Submitted: March 2026 ▪ Accepted: March 2026 ▪ Refereed Anonymously

